

Great Temple of Tenayuca

By Israel Elizalde Mendez, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesoamerican Religions, Religious Place, Archaeological Site, Chichimeca

The city of Tenayuca, which means "walled place", is located in the north part of the Basin of Mexico, in what is today Tlanepantla de Baz in Mexico State. According to the Xolotl Codex, it was built around the year 1200 CE. However, based on the archaeological excavations carried out during the 20th century, an occupation from the 9th century has been documented. Its most important building is the Great Temple, with its distinctive double staircase that leads to two shrines, similar to the Mexica's "Huei teocalli" (Great Temple) of Tenochtitlan. Several archaeological excavations have uncovered mural paintings, sculptures, and human burials.

Date Range: 800 CE - 1521 CE

Region: Basin of Mexico

Region tags: Mexico, Mesoamerica, Basin of Mexico

Tenayuca was located in the north part of the Basin of Mexico (800-1521 CE). The map shows the excavated area and the current archaeological zone, where the main temple is located.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Palacios, Enrique Juan 1935 "La cintura de serpientes de la Pirámide de Tenayuca", en Tenayuca. Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de este lugar, hecho por el Departamento de Monumentos de la Secretaría de Educación Pública, México, Talleres Gráficos del Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Historia y Etnografía, pp. 233-263.
- Source 2: Palacios, Enrique, Juan 1935 "Esculturas y relieves de Tenayuca", en Tenayuca. Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de este lugar, hecho por el Departamento de Monumentos de la Secretaría de Educación Pública, México, Talleres Gráficos del Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Historia y Etnografía, pp. 265-280.
- Source 3: Marquina, Ignacio 1935, "Estudio arquitectónico", en Tenayuca. Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de este lugar, hecho por el Departamento de Monumentos de la Secretaría de Educación Pública, México, Talleres Gráficos del Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Historia y Etnografía, pp. 77-102.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

- Source 1: Caso, Alfonso 1935 "El Templo de Tenayuca estaba dedicado al culto solar", en Tenayuca. Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de este lugar, hecho por el Departamento de Monumentos de la Secretaría de Educación Pública, México, Talleres Gráficos del Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Historia y Etnografía, pp. 293-308.
- Source 2: Noguera, Eduardo 1969 "Excavaciones en sitios postclásicos del valle de México (Culhuacán, Tenayuca, Texcoco, Zapotitlán)", *Anales de Antropología*, núm. 6, 197-231.
- Source 3: Acosta, Jorge R. 1965 "Tenayuca, Exploraciones de 1963", *Anales del INAH*, vol. 6, núm. 17, 117-126.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

- Source 1: Hernández, Haydee L. 2004 "El proyecto de Tenayuca y la comunidad arqueológica en México: 1925-1935", en *Alarifes, amanuenses y evangelistas. Tradiciones, personajes, comunidades y narrativas de la ciencia en México*, Mechthild Rutsch y Mette Marie Wachter (coords.), México, INAH, pp. 325-349..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://thouvenotmarc.com/textos/codice_xolotl.html
- Source 1 Description: Codice Xólotl
- Source 2 URL: https://mediateca.inah.gob.mx/islandora_74/islandora/object/sitioprehispanico%3A2180
- Source 2 Description: Tenayuca, Lugares del INAH
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m5PSP4Rk8J8>
- Source 3 Description: Reproduction of "Altar Tzompantli"

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: It was first excavated by Ignacio Marquina between 1925-1928, later two projects were carried out directed by Jorge Acosta in 1963 and finally by Eduardo Noguera in 1967.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: "Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de Tenayuca" and "Exploraciones de 1963"

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Residential areas

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Religious and domestic ensembles

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: Buried and abandoned

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Natural phenomena

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Specify

– King or emperor

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 90

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 2500

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Clay

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Plaster

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Wood

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Lime

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ On the inside:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The pyramid is surrounded by different types of snakes, both heads and full snakes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Xiuhcóatl "Fire serpent"

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Reliefs representing snakes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Type

–Secco

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Human skull and crossed bones are represented in the painting

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Humans

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Human narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: tezcacuitlapilli, yacametzli, glifo del año, macuáhuítl, chimalli, flechas, bandera, átlatl. At this site, we can also find representations of diverse symbols associated with war and social status, such as: arrows, flags "tezcacuitlapilli, yacametzli, macuáhuítl, chimalli, and átlatl"

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Other

– Other [specify]: Ritual burials

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE
Region: Valley of Mexico

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: It is considered that the representations of Xiuhcoatl, the reliefs of shields, flags and earmuffs are an allusion to the cult of the solar god.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: human heads, incense burners and ceramic vessels were found.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: gold ornaments, copper bells, projectile points, obsidian beads and earrings, and even a green stone plaque.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Ceramic pots and bowls

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Human burials with associated offerings are also found

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are festivals present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: the Xolotl codex describes the founding of Tenayuca. Likewise, Fernando Alva Ixtlilxochitl in his text "Obras Historicas" narrates the foundation and the main rulers of this city

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Alva Ixtlilxochitl (1891, 1: 86-87) describes how Xolotl, a Chichimeca lord, decided to found his capital in the city of Tenayuca, on the border of the Valley of Mexico.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Valley of Mexico

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Juan Palacios Enrique, Alfonso Caso , Moisés Herrera , Ignacio Marquina. Tenayuca. Estudio arqueológico de la pirámide de este lugar, hecho por el Departamento de Monumentos de la Secretaría de Educación Pública. México 1935-2010. Mexico: Conaculta-INAH.